
**JOB SATISFACTION AMONG HIGHER SECONDARY SCHOOL
TEACHERS IN KOLHAPUR AND SUBRURAL AREA- A STUDY**

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Introduction :-

Personality development is the development of organized pattern of behaviours and attitude that make a person distinctive but affective job satisfaction for individuals the reflect of the degree of pleasure in their job. The job satisfaction is how content an individual with his or her job satisfaction with particular facets of their jobs. Such as monthly pay, pension and non-pension arrangement, working hours etc. At most general level of conceptualization, job satisfaction is simply how content and individual is with his or her.

Traditional job satisfaction facets includes co-workers, pay, pension, job conditions, supervision nature of the work and benefits. Job satisfaction is an emotional affective response as a result of his/ her estimation of the degree to which some fact of job reality is congruent or incongruent with his/ her values. Job satisfaction to constitute an attitudinal variable that measure how to person feels about his job including different facets of the job.

• **Objectives of the research study.**

- 1) To find out the different between male and female teachers in respect of their job satisfaction.
- 2) To find out the different between teachers who are working in government and private school in respect at their job satisfaction.
- 3) To find out the different between private aided and unaided higher secondary school teachers in respect at their job satisfaction.

- **Hypothesis of research study.**

- 1) There is no significant different between male and female teachers in respect of their job satisfaction.
- 2) There is no significant difference between teachers who are working in government and private schools in respect at their job satisfaction.
- 3) There is no significant different between private aided and unaided school teachers in respect of their job satisfaction.

- **Methodology for the study.**

In the present study, the researcher used the survey method and experimental method to study the job satisfaction among higher secondary school teacher.

- **Tools used in the research study**

The tools used for questionnaires, pre-test, post-test, collected using standardized teachers job satisfaction scale. The teacher makes the item relating job satisfaction credit is given.

- **Sample**

Population of the present study consists of 100 higher secondary school teacher from Kolhapur and sub rural (talukawise) selected randomly.

100 higher secondary school teachers from Kolhapur and sub rural selected randomly in such way 50 teachers are from private school and 50 teachers are from government in Zilla Parishad schools.

50 teachers working with private school are random selected in such way that out of these 50. 25 teachers are working with aided schools and 25 are working with unaided higher secondary school.

This study is related with the job satisfaction of secondary school teachers working in Marathi medium schools only.

- **Limitations of the study**

This study is restricted with job satisfaction of male and female teachers, married &

unmarried teachers, government and private teachers, aided and unaided higher secondary school teachers.

- **Analysis and Interpretation of data**

The research data is analyzed using mean, standard deviation (S.D.) t-test etc.

Null Hypothesis- 1

There is no significant difference between male and female teachers in respect of their job satisfaction.

Table No.1

The table showing mean, S.D. and calculated t-value at male and female teachers in their job satisfaction.

Gender	No.	Mean	S.D.	t-value
Female	60	172.42	15.08	6.72
Male	40	167.76	12.45	

The test has been applied to find out whether is any significant difference in job satisfaction with respect to their gender the calculated t-value is found to be 6.72 which is greater than the table value and significant at 0.05 level. Hence the null hypothesis there is no significant difference between male & female teachers in respect of their job satisfaction is rejected there fore it is concluded that there is a significant difference between male and female teachers in the job satisfaction. This means that the female teachers are more satisfied with their job compared to the male teachers.

Null Hypothesis -2

There is no significant difference between teachers working in government and private schools in respect of their job satisfaction.

Table No.2

The table showing mean, S.D. and calculated t-value of government and private teachers in their job satisfaction.

School Type	No.	Mean	S.D.	t-value
Private	50	165.58	16.32	3.96
Government	50	158.37	12.41	

The t-test has been applied to find out whether there is any significant difference in the job satisfaction with respect to types of school the calculated t-value is found to be 3.96 which is greater than the table value and significant at 0.05 level. Hence the null hypothesis there is no significant difference between government and private teacher in respect at their job satisfaction is rejected there is significant difference between government and private teachers in the job satisfaction this means that the private school teacher has more job satisfaction than the government school teachers.

Null Hypothesis- 3

There is no significant difference between private aided and unaided school teachers in respect at their job satisfaction.

Table No.3

The table showing mean, S.D. and calculated t-value of private aided and unaided teachers in their job satisfaction.

Status	No.	Mean	S.D.	t-value
Unaided	25	191.58	14.68	11.94
Aided	25	146.18	11.81	

The t test has been applied to find out whether there is any significant difference in the job satisfaction with respects to financial. The calculated t- value is found to be 11.94 which is greater than the table value and significant at 0.05 level. Hence the Null Hypothesis there is no significant difference between aided and unaided school teachers with respect of their job satisfaction is rejected. Therefore it is concluded that there is significant difference between aided & unaided school teachers in the

job satisfaction. This means that the aided school teachers are satisfied with their jobs, compared to the unaided school teachers.

Major finding

- 1) Male and female school teachers differ significantly in their job satisfaction male teacher have high job satisfaction than their teachers female.
- 2) Private and government school teachers differ significantly in their job satisfaction. Private teacher have high job satisfaction than government teachers.
- 3) Aided and unaided school teacher differ significantly in their job satisfaction. Aided school teacher have high job satisfaction than unaided higher secondary school teachers.

Conclusion

The job satisfaction know self is important. Person must know that what kinds at work tasks one activities are attractive to self. Human being have different physical, Psychological and social needs when these need are not promptly easily satisfied by them, an individual face condition of stress.

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